

For Project: 13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB
 Project Notes:
 Location/Name: Incoming - Southbound
 Report Generated: 11/25/2022 11:04
 Speed Intervals 1 km/h
 Time Intervals Instant
 Traffic Report From 11/22/2022 00:00:00 through
 85th Percentile Speed 59 km/h
 85th Percentile Vehicles 14470
 Max Speed 91 km/h on 11/23/2022
 Total Vehicles 17023
 AADT: 5674

Volumes - weekly counts

Time	5 Day
Average Daily	5674
AM Peak 11:30	442
PM Peak 04:30	512

Speed

Speed Limit: 50
 85th Percentile Speed: 59
 50th Percentile Speed: 53
 10 km/h Pace Interval: 48.0 km/h to 58.0 km/h
 Average Speed: 53.35

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday
Count over limit	N/A	4095	4095
% over limit	N/A	72.4	72.9
Avg Speeder	N/A	55.8	55.8

Class Counts

	Number	%
VEH_SM	12	0.1
VEH_MED	16659	97.9
VEH_LG	352	2.1
[VEH_SM=motorcycle,	VEH_MED = sedan,	VEH_LG = tri

Day/Time Ending	85th pctl (km/h)	85th pctl cnts	Total Cnts
11/22/2022 01:00:00 AM	65.0	21	25
11/22/2022 02:00:00 AM	58.0	10	12
11/22/2022 03:00:00 AM	60.0	12	14
11/22/2022 04:00:00 AM	55.0	8	10
11/22/2022 05:00:00 AM	58.0	14	17
11/22/2022 06:00:00 AM	58.0	37	43
11/22/2022 07:00:00 AM	60.0	175	206
11/22/2022 08:00:00 AM	59.0	232	273
11/22/2022 09:00:00 AM	59.0	270	318
11/22/2022 10:00:00 AM	60.0	214	252
11/22/2022 11:00:00 AM	59.0	269	317

11/22/2022 12:00:00 PM	59.0	311	366
11/22/2022 01:00:00 PM	59.0	366	431
11/22/2022 02:00:00 PM	59.0	367	432
11/22/2022 03:00:00 PM	58.0	393	462
11/22/2022 04:00:00 PM	58.0	431	507
11/22/2022 05:00:00 PM	58.0	431	507
11/22/2022 06:00:00 PM	57.0	392	461
11/22/2022 07:00:00 PM	58.0	254	299
11/22/2022 08:00:00 PM	57.0	192	226
11/22/2022 09:00:00 PM	58.0	166	195
11/22/2022 10:00:00 PM	58.0	116	136
11/22/2022 11:00:00 PM	59.0	83	98
11/23/2022 12:00:00 AM	59.0	44	52
11/23/2022 01:00:00 AM	61.0	27	32
11/23/2022 02:00:00 AM	61.0	10	12
11/23/2022 03:00:00 AM	60.0	8	10
11/23/2022 04:00:00 AM	67.0	5	6
11/23/2022 05:00:00 AM	63.0	13	15
11/23/2022 06:00:00 AM	57.0	39	46
11/23/2022 07:00:00 AM	57.0	154	181
11/23/2022 08:00:00 AM	57.0	238	280
11/23/2022 09:00:00 AM	60.0	278	327
11/23/2022 10:00:00 AM	59.0	231	272
11/23/2022 11:00:00 AM	59.0	275	323
11/23/2022 12:00:00 PM	60.0	351	413
11/23/2022 01:00:00 PM	59.0	369	434
11/23/2022 02:00:00 PM	58.0	363	427
11/23/2022 03:00:00 PM	59.0	386	454
11/23/2022 04:00:00 PM	58.0	371	437
11/23/2022 05:00:00 PM	57.0	418	492
11/23/2022 06:00:00 PM	58.0	350	412
11/23/2022 07:00:00 PM	57.0	240	282
11/23/2022 08:00:00 PM	57.0	196	230
11/23/2022 09:00:00 PM	58.0	183	215
11/23/2022 10:00:00 PM	58.0	135	159
11/23/2022 11:00:00 PM	57.0	93	109
11/24/2022 12:00:00 AM	59.0	44	52
11/24/2022 01:00:00 AM	62.0	31	37
11/24/2022 02:00:00 AM	61.0	15	18
11/24/2022 03:00:00 AM	64.0	20	23
11/24/2022 04:00:00 AM	61.0	10	12
11/24/2022 05:00:00 AM	57.0	16	19
11/24/2022 06:00:00 AM	57.0	40	47
11/24/2022 07:00:00 AM	60.0	161	189
11/24/2022 08:00:00 AM	59.0	232	273
11/24/2022 09:00:00 AM	58.0	270	318
11/24/2022 10:00:00 AM	58.0	230	270
11/24/2022 11:00:00 AM	58.0	282	332
11/24/2022 12:00:00 PM	59.0	359	422
11/24/2022 01:00:00 PM	59.0	352	414
11/24/2022 02:00:00 PM	59.0	358	421
11/24/2022 03:00:00 PM	59.0	345	406

11/24/2022 04:00:00 PM	58.0	390	459
11/24/2022 05:00:00 PM	58.0	434	511
11/24/2022 06:00:00 PM	57.0	365	429
11/24/2022 07:00:00 PM	58.0	298	350
11/24/2022 08:00:00 PM	59.0	224	264
11/24/2022 09:00:00 PM	60.0	168	198
11/24/2022 10:00:00 PM	59.0	146	172
11/24/2022 11:00:00 PM	60.0	94	110
11/25/2022 12:00:00 AM	61.0	43	51

Day/Time Ending	85th pctl (km/h)	85th pctl cnts	Total Cnts
11/23/2022 12:00:00 AM	59.0	4810	5659
11/24/2022 12:00:00 AM	58.0	4776	5619
11/24/2022 11:59:59 PM	59.0	4883	5745

11/24/2022

23:59:59

00:00:33

7 Day

5674

442

512

Thursday

4251

74.0

55.8

Friday

N/A

N/A

N/A

Saturday

N/A

N/A

N/A

uck]

Max Speed

75

59

66

63

76

74

72

77

70

70

71

Avg Speeder

58.6

55.7

56.6

56.0

58.3

55.4

56.3

55.9

55.8

56.4

55.9

% Speeders

84.0%

75.0%

92.9%

60.0%

70.6%

86.0%

79.6%

77.3%

77.0%

77.8%

74.4%

69	55.8	78.1%
68	56.1	74.2%
72	55.7	76.6%
80	55.4	73.2%
68	55.3	73.2%
73	55.5	67.1%
72	55.5	62.7%
72	55.9	58.5%
69	55.0	72.1%
67	55.6	63.6%
79	55.6	72.8%
73	56.7	77.6%
85	57.4	63.5%
91	58.0	78.1%
62	56.4	83.3%
77	59.1	90.0%
68	59.5	100.0%
65	58.3	66.7%
67	54.8	69.6%
70	54.9	65.7%
71	55.6	67.5%
82	56.2	74.3%
68	56.2	80.1%
79	55.9	80.8%
71	56.2	77.2%
73	56.3	74.9%
76	55.9	79.4%
70	56.1	76.7%
71	55.5	71.2%
71	55.2	63.0%
75	55.5	68.2%
79	55.1	71.3%
75	55.3	65.2%
72	55.6	70.7%
70	55.4	75.5%
69	55.8	71.6%
72	56.2	76.9%
72	58.5	78.4%
69	57.5	72.2%
76	60.3	82.6%
64	56.1	83.3%
65	56.1	73.7%
71	55.6	70.2%
73	56.5	82.0%
75	56.0	74.0%
76	55.5	73.0%
66	55.7	80.0%
71	55.8	72.9%
75	55.8	77.3%
71	55.8	77.1%
77	55.8	77.9%
75	55.7	75.4%

69	55.6	68.8%
70	55.5	66.7%
76	55.2	71.6%
79	55.5	66.6%
77	55.6	75.0%
80	56.8	78.3%
67	55.9	74.4%
77	57.1	80.0%
68	57.1	80.4%

Max Speed	Avg Speeder	% Speeders
85	55.8	72.4%
91	55.8	72.9%
80	55.8	74.0%

Sunday

N/A

N/A

N/A

Incoming Weekly Counts

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB

from Tue-Nov-22-202

Hour	11/21/2022	to	11/27/2022		
	Monday 11/21/2022	Tuesday 11/22/2022	Wednesday 11/23/2022	Thursday 11/24/2022	Friday 11/25/2022
0 - 1	0	25	32	37	0
1 - 2	0	12	12	18	0
2 - 3	0	14	10	23	0
3 - 4	0	10	6	12	0
4 - 5	0	17	15	19	0
5 - 6	0	43	46	47	0
6 - 7	0	206	181	189	0
7 - 8	0	273	280	273	0
8 - 9	0	318	327	318	0
9 - 10	0	252	271	270	0
10 - 11	0	317	323	332	0
11 - 12	0	366	413	422	0
12 - 13	0	431	434	414	0
13 - 14	0	432	427	421	0
14 - 15	0	462	454	406	0
15 - 16	0	507	437	459	0
16 - 17	0	507	492	511	0
17 - 18	0	461	412	429	0
18 - 19	0	299	282	350	0
19 - 20	0	226	230	264	0
20 - 21	0	195	215	198	0
21 - 22	0	136	159	172	0
22 - 23	0	98	109	110	0
23 - 24	0	52	52	51	0
Totals	0	5659	5619	5745	0
% of Total	0%	33.24%	33.01%	33.75%	0%

Saturday	Sunday	Week	Weekend	Week Day 85%
11/26/2022	11/27/2022	Day Avg	Avg	Avg Speed
0	0	31.33	0	62.5
0	0	14	0	59.5
0	0	15.67	0	61.33
0	0	9.33	0	60.83
0	0	17	0	59.33
0	0	45.33	0	57.03
0	0	192	0	58.5
0	0	275.33	0	58
0	0	321	0	58.57
0	0	264.33	0	58.63
0	0	324	0	58.47
0	0	400.33	0	58.7
0	0	426.33	0	58.67
0	0	426.67	0	58.3
0	0	440.67	0	58.13
0	0	467.67	0	57.47
0	0	503.33	0	57.37
0	0	434	0	57
0	0	310.33	0	57.43
0	0	240	0	57.27
0	0	202.67	0	58.07
0	0	155.67	0	57.77
0	0	105.67	0	58.67
0	0	51.67	0	59.37
0	0			
0%	0%			

Incoming Monthly Counts

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB

from Tue-Nov-22-2022-12-00-AM

Hour	Nov 2022					
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
0 - 1	0	25	32	37	0	0
1 - 2	0	12	12	18	0	0
2 - 3	0	14	10	23	0	0
3 - 4	0	10	6	12	0	0
4 - 5	0	17	15	19	0	0
5 - 6	0	43	46	47	0	0
6 - 7	0	206	181	189	0	0
7 - 8	0	273	280	273	0	0
8 - 9	0	318	327	318	0	0
9 - 10	0	252	271	270	0	0
10 - 11	0	317	323	332	0	0
11 - 12	0	366	413	422	0	0
12 - 13	0	431	434	414	0	0
13 - 14	0	432	427	421	0	0
14 - 15	0	462	454	406	0	0
15 - 16	0	507	437	459	0	0
16 - 17	0	507	492	511	0	0
17 - 18	0	461	412	429	0	0
18 - 19	0	299	282	350	0	0
19 - 20	0	226	230	264	0	0
20 - 21	0	195	215	198	0	0
21 - 22	0	136	159	172	0	0
22 - 23	0	98	109	110	0	0
23 - 24	0	52	52	51	0	0
Totals	0	5659	5619	5745	0	0
% of Total	0%	33.24%	33.01%	33.75%	0%	0%

Sunday	Week Day Avg	Weekend Avg	Week Day 85% Avg Speed
0	31.33	0	62.5
0	14	0	59.5
0	15.67	0	61.33
0	9.33	0	60.83
0	17	0	59.33
0	45.33	0	57.03
0	192	0	58.5
0	275.33	0	58
0	321	0	58.57
0	264.33	0	58.63
0	324	0	58.47
0	400.33	0	58.7
0	426.33	0	58.67
0	426.67	0	58.3
0	440.67	0	58.13
0	467.67	0	57.47
0	503.33	0	57.37
0	434	0	57
0	310.33	0	57.43
0	240	0	57.27
0	202.67	0	58.07
0	155.67	0	57.77
0	105.67	0	58.67
0	51.67	0	59.37
0			
0%			

Incoming Weekly Speeds

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB

from Tue-Nov-22-202

	11/21/2022	to	11/27/2022		
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
Hour	11/21/2022	11/22/2022	11/23/2022	11/24/2022	11/25/2022
0 - 1	0	56.88	55.66	55.7	0
1 - 2	0	52.33	54.17	55.11	0
2 - 3	0	56	56.6	57.61	0
3 - 4	0	51.5	59.5	54.83	0
4 - 5	0	55	54.8	53.32	0
5 - 6	0	54.3	52.5	53.38	0
6 - 7	0	54.48	52.37	54.9	0
7 - 8	0	53.87	52.65	53.66	0
8 - 9	0	53.67	53.57	53.19	0
9 - 10	0	54.35	54.29	54.05	0
10 - 11	0	53.68	54.08	53.52	0
11 - 12	0	53.97	54.12	53.79	0
12 - 13	0	53.35	53.81	53.72	0
13 - 14	0	53.83	53.95	53.94	0
14 - 15	0	52.99	53.87	53.1	0
15 - 16	0	53.06	52.93	52.71	0
16 - 17	0	52.52	51.93	52.52	0
17 - 18	0	52.41	52.62	52.79	0
18 - 19	0	51.92	52.74	52.63	0
19 - 20	0	52.5	52.51	53.36	0
20 - 21	0	52.16	53.04	54.55	0
21 - 22	0	53.38	53.21	53.6	0
22 - 23	0	54.48	53.5	54.99	0
23 - 24	0	53.81	54.4	55.37	0
Totals	0	1286.5	1292.7	1296.3	0
% of Total	0%	33.2%	33.36%	33.45%	0%

Saturday	Sunday	Week	Weekend	Week Day 85%
11/26/2022	11/27/2022	Day Avg	Avg	Avg Speed
0	0	56	0	62.5
0	0	54.05	0	59.5
0	0	56.91	0	61.33
0	0	54.64	0	60.83
0	0	54.31	0	59.33
0	0	53.38	0	57.03
0	0	53.96	0	58.5
0	0	53.38	0	58
0	0	53.48	0	58.57
0	0	54.23	0	58.63
0	0	53.76	0	58.47
0	0	53.96	0	58.7
0	0	53.63	0	58.67
0	0	53.91	0	58.3
0	0	53.33	0	58.13
0	0	52.9	0	57.47
0	0	52.33	0	57.37
0	0	52.6	0	57
0	0	52.44	0	57.43
0	0	52.82	0	57.27
0	0	53.25	0	58.07
0	0	53.4	0	57.77
0	0	54.32	0	58.67
0	0	54.52	0	59.37
0	0			
0%	0%			

Incoming Monthly Speeds

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB

from Tue-Nov-22-2022-12-00-AM to Thu-Nov-

Hour	Nov 2022						
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
0 - 1	0	56.88	55.66	55.7	0	0	0
1 - 2	0	52.33	54.17	55.11	0	0	0
2 - 3	0	56	56.6	57.61	0	0	0
3 - 4	0	51.5	59.5	54.83	0	0	0
4 - 5	0	55	54.8	53.32	0	0	0
5 - 6	0	54.3	52.5	53.38	0	0	0
6 - 7	0	54.48	52.37	54.9	0	0	0
7 - 8	0	53.87	52.65	53.66	0	0	0
8 - 9	0	53.67	53.57	53.19	0	0	0
9 - 10	0	54.35	54.29	54.05	0	0	0
10 - 11	0	53.68	54.08	53.52	0	0	0
11 - 12	0	53.97	54.12	53.79	0	0	0
12 - 13	0	53.35	53.81	53.72	0	0	0
13 - 14	0	53.83	53.95	53.94	0	0	0
14 - 15	0	52.99	53.87	53.1	0	0	0
15 - 16	0	53.06	52.93	52.71	0	0	0
16 - 17	0	52.52	51.93	52.52	0	0	0
17 - 18	0	52.41	52.62	52.79	0	0	0
18 - 19	0	51.92	52.74	52.63	0	0	0
19 - 20	0	52.5	52.51	53.36	0	0	0
20 - 21	0	52.16	53.04	54.55	0	0	0
21 - 22	0	53.38	53.21	53.6	0	0	0
22 - 23	0	54.48	53.5	54.99	0	0	0
23 - 24	0	53.81	54.4	55.37	0	0	0

Week Day Avg	Weekend Avg	Week Day 85% Avg Speed
56	0	62.5
54.05	0	59.5
56.91	0	61.33
54.64	0	60.83
54.31	0	59.33
53.38	0	57.03
53.96	0	58.5
53.38	0	58
53.48	0	58.57
54.23	0	58.63
53.76	0	58.47
53.96	0	58.7
53.63	0	58.67
53.91	0	58.3
53.33	0	58.13
52.9	0	57.47
52.33	0	57.37
52.6	0	57
52.44	0	57.43
52.82	0	57.27
53.25	0	58.07
53.4	0	57.77
54.32	0	58.67
54.52	0	59.37

Incoming Weekly EightyFifthSpeeds
 13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB

from Tue-Nov-22-202

	11/21/2022	to	11/27/2022		
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
Hour	11/21/2022	11/22/2022	11/23/2022	11/24/2022	11/25/2022
0 - 1	0	65	60.5	62	0
1 - 2	0	57.5	60.5	60.5	0
2 - 3	0	60	60	64	0
3 - 4	0	55	67	60.5	0
4 - 5	0	58	63	57	0
5 - 6	0	58	56.3	56.8	0
6 - 7	0	59.3	57	59.2	0
7 - 8	0	58.2	57	58.8	0
8 - 9	0	58.7	59.1	57.9	0
9 - 10	0	59.2	58.9	57.8	0
10 - 11	0	58.6	58.8	58	0
11 - 12	0	58.4	59.2	58.5	0
12 - 13	0	58.8	58.9	58.3	0
13 - 14	0	58.5	58	58.4	0
14 - 15	0	57.3	58.6	58.5	0
15 - 16	0	57.4	57.3	57.7	0
16 - 17	0	57.8	56.9	57.4	0
17 - 18	0	56.8	57.2	57	0
18 - 19	0	57.8	57	57.5	0
19 - 20	0	56.9	56.8	58.1	0
20 - 21	0	57.2	57.2	59.8	0
21 - 22	0	57.8	57.3	58.2	0
22 - 23	0	59	57	60	0
23 - 24	0	59	58.4	60.7	0
Totals	0	1400.2	1407.9	1412.6	0
% of Total	0%	33.17%	33.36%	33.47%	0%

Saturday	Sunday	Week	Weekend	Week Day 85%
11/26/2022	11/27/2022	Day Avg	Avg	Avg Speed
0	0	62.5	0	62.5
0	0	59.5	0	59.5
0	0	61.33	0	61.33
0	0	60.83	0	60.83
0	0	59.33	0	59.33
0	0	57.03	0	57.03
0	0	58.5	0	58.5
0	0	58	0	58
0	0	58.57	0	58.57
0	0	58.63	0	58.63
0	0	58.47	0	58.47
0	0	58.7	0	58.7
0	0	58.67	0	58.67
0	0	58.3	0	58.3
0	0	58.13	0	58.13
0	0	57.47	0	57.47
0	0	57.37	0	57.37
0	0	57	0	57
0	0	57.43	0	57.43
0	0	57.27	0	57.27
0	0	58.07	0	58.07
0	0	57.77	0	57.77
0	0	58.67	0	58.67
0	0	59.37	0	59.37
0	0			
0%	0%			

Incoming Monthly EightyFifthSpeeds
13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB

from Tue-Nov-22-2022-12-00-AM to Thu-Nov-

Hour	Nov 2022						
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
0 - 1	0	65	60.5	62	0	0	0
1 - 2	0	57.5	60.5	60.5	0	0	0
2 - 3	0	60	60	64	0	0	0
3 - 4	0	55	67	60.5	0	0	0
4 - 5	0	58	63	57	0	0	0
5 - 6	0	58	56.3	56.8	0	0	0
6 - 7	0	59.3	57	59.2	0	0	0
7 - 8	0	58.2	57	58.8	0	0	0
8 - 9	0	58.7	59.1	57.9	0	0	0
9 - 10	0	59.2	58.9	57.8	0	0	0
10 - 11	0	58.6	58.8	58	0	0	0
11 - 12	0	58.4	59.2	58.5	0	0	0
12 - 13	0	58.8	58.9	58.3	0	0	0
13 - 14	0	58.5	58	58.4	0	0	0
14 - 15	0	57.3	58.6	58.5	0	0	0
15 - 16	0	57.4	57.3	57.7	0	0	0
16 - 17	0	57.8	56.9	57.4	0	0	0
17 - 18	0	56.8	57.2	57	0	0	0
18 - 19	0	57.8	57	57.5	0	0	0
19 - 20	0	56.9	56.8	58.1	0	0	0
20 - 21	0	57.2	57.2	59.8	0	0	0
21 - 22	0	57.8	57.3	58.2	0	0	0
22 - 23	0	59	57	60	0	0	0
23 - 24	0	59	58.4	60.7	0	0	0

Week Day Avg	Weekend Avg	Week Day 85% Avg Speed
62.5	0	62.5
59.5	0	59.5
61.33	0	61.33
60.83	0	60.83
59.33	0	59.33
57.03	0	57.03
58.5	0	58.5
58	0	58
58.57	0	58.57
58.63	0	58.63
58.47	0	58.47
58.7	0	58.7
58.67	0	58.67
58.3	0	58.3
58.13	0	58.13
57.47	0	57.47
57.37	0	57.37
57	0	57
57.43	0	57.43
57.27	0	57.27
58.07	0	58.07
57.77	0	57.77
58.67	0	58.67
59.37	0	59.37

RADAR MOTOR VEHICLE SPEED

Date: 11/22/2022 County: [redacted] Hwy: [redacted] Location: [redacted]
 Time (from): 12:00 AM (to): 11:59 PM Weather: [redacted]
 Surface Type: [redacted] Surface Condition: [redacted] Wet: [redacted] Dry: [redacted] Smo: [redacted]

km/h	AUTOMOBILES Direction:	Cumulative Total	AUTOMOBILES Direction:	Cumulative Total	TRUCKS Direction:
>= 80		6			
79		11			
78		11			
77		17			
76		23			
75		30			
74		34			
73		44			
72		58			
71		77			
70		108			
69		142			
68		195			
67		256			
66		357			
65		504			
64		650			
63		844			
62		1110			
61		1523			

60

2023

|||||

59

2627

|||||

58

3318

|||||

57

4254

||||| ||||| |||||

|

56

5528

55

6892

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

50

[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

13502

[REDACTED]

49

[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

14333

[REDACTED]

48

[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

15036

[REDACTED]

47

[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

15589

[REDACTED]

46

[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

15934

[REDACTED]

17023

x 0.85

x 0.85

85th Percentile Vehicles (counts)

14470

85th Percentile Vehicles (counts)

85th Percentile Speed

59

85th Percentile Speed

Form 1882
(Rev. 03/19)

Month: Rough:

& BUSES Direction:	km/h
	>= 80
	79
	78
	77
	76
	75
	74
	73
	72
	71
	70
	69
	68
	67
	66
	65
	64
	63
	62
	61

56

55

54

53

52

51

Starting Hour	Count	Average Speed of all Traffic	Violator Counts	Average Speed of Violators
00:00:00	32	56.2	25	58.4
00:15:00	27	56.1	22	57.8
00:30:00	17	56.5	14	60.1
00:45:00	18	55.1	14	57.4
01:00:00	17	51.8	11	55.1
01:15:00	10	53.4	8	56.0
01:30:00	5	52.6	3	55.3
01:45:00	10	59.3	10	59.3
02:00:00	9	56.9	8	58.0
02:15:00	17	55.9	14	58.8
02:30:00	9	58.6	8	59.8
02:45:00	12	57.2	11	59.0
03:00:00	6	56.7	5	60.4
03:15:00	2	58.0	2	58.0
03:30:00	9	54.6	7	57.0
03:45:00	11	53.0	8	54.6
04:00:00	15	57.7	14	58.2
04:15:00	7	52.0	3	59.7
04:30:00	14	52.8	7	59.0
04:45:00	15	53.5	12	55.2
05:00:00	28	52.3	20	53.9
05:15:00	22	52.6	14	55.4
05:30:00	46	54.4	38	55.7
05:45:00	40	53.3	30	55.6
06:00:00	77	52.6	52	55.2
06:15:00	118	54.7	98	56.1
06:30:00	192	53.7	138	56.3
06:45:00	189	54.3	150	55.9
07:00:00	126	54.5	101	56.3
07:15:00	161	53.3	111	56.1
07:30:00	257	53.2	181	55.8
07:45:00	282	53.1	209	55.4
08:00:00	218	53.1	161	55.5
08:15:00	286	52.8	203	55.7
08:30:00	217	54.1	164	56.3
08:45:00	242	54.1	192	55.9
09:00:00	206	54.3	167	56.0
09:15:00	167	54.9	137	56.3
09:30:00	186	53.6	133	56.2
09:45:00	234	54.2	192	56.0
10:00:00	238	53.9	189	55.7
10:15:00	233	54.0	177	55.9
10:30:00	239	54.1	184	56.0
10:45:00	262	53.1	189	55.8
11:00:00	266	53.5	196	55.7
11:15:00	266	53.9	204	56.1
11:30:00	341	54.2	266	56.1
11:45:00	328	54.1	265	55.9
12:00:00	362	53.2	259	55.9
12:15:00	297	53.7	227	55.9
12:30:00	301	54.0	230	56.2
12:45:00	319	53.6	248	56.2
13:00:00	328	53.7	265	55.3

13:15:00	315	54.1	240	56.1
13:30:00	326	54.5	264	56.3
13:45:00	311	53.3	229	55.6
14:00:00	280	53.6	218	55.5
14:15:00	337	53.2	241	56.0
14:30:00	346	53.2	260	55.6
14:45:00	359	53.4	273	55.8
15:00:00	352	53.6	272	55.6
15:15:00	347	53.0	251	55.5
15:30:00	348	52.4	244	55.1
15:45:00	356	52.7	231	55.6
16:00:00	369	53.3	281	55.3
16:15:00	338	51.9	208	55.7
16:30:00	457	51.6	274	55.1
16:45:00	346	52.7	228	55.7
17:00:00	382	52.4	251	55.4
17:15:00	352	52.7	229	55.6
17:30:00	305	52.7	213	55.3
17:45:00	263	52.7	184	55.2
18:00:00	263	52.5	168	55.2
18:15:00	229	52.5	148	55.6
18:30:00	244	52.1	163	55.2
18:45:00	195	52.7	130	56.0
19:00:00	200	52.4	132	55.2
19:15:00	187	52.2	121	55.1
19:30:00	168	54.1	139	55.7
19:45:00	165	52.8	119	55.5
20:00:00	144	53.3	107	55.9
20:15:00	171	52.9	114	56.2
20:30:00	163	53.1	115	55.6
20:45:00	130	53.8	95	56.5
21:00:00	155	53.4	113	55.7
21:15:00	129	53.5	97	55.5
21:30:00	103	53.8	81	55.6
21:45:00	80	52.7	56	55.8
22:00:00	93	53.4	62	56.7
22:15:00	78	53.5	58	55.5
22:30:00	78	54.6	64	56.3
22:45:00	68	56.3	58	57.6
23:00:00	61	54.9	46	57.0
23:15:00	34	54.0	23	56.6
23:30:00	28	55.9	24	57.4
23:45:00	32	53.1	21	56.4

Incoming Histogram

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB

Date	Starting Hr:min	<15	15 to <20	20 to <25	25 to <30	30 to <35	35 to <40	40 to <45
11/22/2022	00:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	00:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	00:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	00:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	01:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	01:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/22/2022	01:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	01:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	02:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	02:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	02:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	02:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	03:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/22/2022	03:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	03:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	03:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	04:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	04:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	04:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	04:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	05:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	05:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	05:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	05:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	06:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	06:15	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
11/22/2022	06:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	06:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/22/2022	07:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/22/2022	07:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/22/2022	07:30	0	0	0	0	1	2	2
11/22/2022	07:45	0	0	0	0	1	2	0
11/22/2022	08:00	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11/22/2022	08:15	1	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/22/2022	08:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/22/2022	08:45	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
11/22/2022	09:00	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	09:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	09:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/22/2022	09:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/22/2022	10:00	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
11/22/2022	10:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	10:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	10:45	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	11:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	11:15	0	0	0	0	0	2	4
11/22/2022	11:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	11:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	12:00	0	0	0	1	2	0	11
11/22/2022	12:15	0	1	0	0	0	0	5

11/22/2022	12:30	0	0	0	1	0	0	5
11/22/2022	12:45	1	0	0	0	1	1	2
11/22/2022	13:00	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	13:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/22/2022	13:30	0	0	0	0	1	2	0
11/22/2022	13:45	0	0	0	0	1	0	3
11/22/2022	14:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	8
11/22/2022	14:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	7
11/22/2022	14:30	0	0	0	0	0	2	3
11/22/2022	14:45	0	0	0	0	1	2	2
11/22/2022	15:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/22/2022	15:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/22/2022	15:30	0	0	0	0	2	1	7
11/22/2022	15:45	0	0	0	0	2	0	4
11/22/2022	16:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	6
11/22/2022	16:15	0	0	0	1	0	3	5
11/22/2022	16:30	0	0	0	3	0	2	9
11/22/2022	16:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/22/2022	17:00	0	0	0	0	0	2	9
11/22/2022	17:15	0	0	0	0	0	2	8
11/22/2022	17:30	0	0	0	0	0	3	4
11/22/2022	17:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/22/2022	18:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	4
11/22/2022	18:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/22/2022	18:30	0	0	0	0	0	5	5
11/22/2022	18:45	1	0	0	0	0	1	5
11/22/2022	19:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	19:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	6
11/22/2022	19:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/22/2022	19:45	0	0	0	0	1	1	2
11/22/2022	20:00	0	0	0	0	0	2	3
11/22/2022	20:15	0	0	0	1	0	0	5
11/22/2022	20:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	20:45	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	21:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	21:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	21:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	21:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/22/2022	22:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/22/2022	22:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	22:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/22/2022	22:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	23:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	23:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	23:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	23:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
24 Hr Summary		3	3	2	7	16	60	195

Date	Starting Hr:min	<15	15 to <20	20 to <25	25 to <30	30 to <35	35 to <40	40 to <45
11/23/2022	00:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	00:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	00:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	00:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	01:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

11/23/2022	01:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	01:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	01:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	02:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	02:15	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
11/23/2022	02:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	02:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	03:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	03:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	03:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	03:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	04:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	04:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	04:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	04:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	05:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	05:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	05:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	05:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/23/2022	06:00	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11/23/2022	06:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	06:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/23/2022	06:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/23/2022	07:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/23/2022	07:15	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
11/23/2022	07:30	0	0	0	0	0	3	2
11/23/2022	07:45	0	0	0	0	1	2	6
11/23/2022	08:00	1	0	0	0	1	1	1
11/23/2022	08:15	0	0	0	1	1	1	6
11/23/2022	08:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	08:45	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11/23/2022	09:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/23/2022	09:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	09:30	0	1	0	0	0	2	1
11/23/2022	09:45	0	0	0	0	1	3	0
11/23/2022	10:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	10:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/23/2022	10:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/23/2022	10:45	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/23/2022	11:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/23/2022	11:15	0	0	0	0	0	2	3
11/23/2022	11:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
11/23/2022	11:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/23/2022	12:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
11/23/2022	12:15	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
11/23/2022	12:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
11/23/2022	12:45	1	1	0	0	1	1	3
11/23/2022	13:00	0	0	0	1	0	2	1
11/23/2022	13:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
11/23/2022	13:30	0	0	0	0	0	2	3
11/23/2022	13:45	0	0	0	1	0	1	3
11/23/2022	14:00	0	0	0	0	1	1	3
11/23/2022	14:15	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
11/23/2022	14:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	6

11/23/2022	14:45	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
11/23/2022	15:00	0	0	0	0	1	0	4
11/23/2022	15:15	0	0	0	1	1	1	6
11/23/2022	15:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	6
11/23/2022	15:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/23/2022	16:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	16:15	0	0	0	1	0	1	11
11/23/2022	16:30	0	0	0	0	0	2	16
11/23/2022	16:45	0	0	0	1	1	2	7
11/23/2022	17:00	0	0	0	0	1	0	4
11/23/2022	17:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	17:30	0	0	0	1	2	1	2
11/23/2022	17:45	0	0	0	0	2	1	6
11/23/2022	18:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	18:15	0	0	1	0	0	2	2
11/23/2022	18:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	18:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/23/2022	19:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	5
11/23/2022	19:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/23/2022	19:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	19:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	5
11/23/2022	20:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	20:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/23/2022	20:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/23/2022	20:45	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
11/23/2022	21:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/23/2022	21:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	21:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/23/2022	21:45	0	0	0	0	0	3	1
11/23/2022	22:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	22:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/23/2022	22:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	22:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	23:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	23:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	23:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	23:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
24 Hr Summary		3	2	1	8	19	50	206

Date	Starting Hr:min	<15	15 to <20	20 to <25	25 to <30	30 to <35	35 to <40	40 to <45
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11/24/2022	00:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	00:30	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
11/24/2022	00:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	01:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	01:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	01:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	01:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	02:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	02:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	02:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	02:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/24/2022	03:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	03:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

11/24/2022	03:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	03:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	04:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	04:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	04:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	04:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	05:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	05:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	05:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	05:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	06:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/24/2022	06:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	06:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/24/2022	06:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	07:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	07:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/24/2022	07:30	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
11/24/2022	07:45	0	0	0	0	0	3	0
11/24/2022	08:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/24/2022	08:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	6
11/24/2022	08:30	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11/24/2022	08:45	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
11/24/2022	09:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/24/2022	09:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	09:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	09:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/24/2022	10:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/24/2022	10:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/24/2022	10:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/24/2022	10:45	0	0	1	0	0	1	1
11/24/2022	11:00	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
11/24/2022	11:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	11:30	0	0	0	1	0	2	1
11/24/2022	11:45	0	0	0	0	0	3	2
11/24/2022	12:00	0	0	0	0	1	1	2
11/24/2022	12:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/24/2022	12:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	12:45	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	13:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	13:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/24/2022	13:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/24/2022	13:45	0	0	0	1	1	0	4
11/24/2022	14:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	14:15	0	1	0	0	1	2	5
11/24/2022	14:30	0	0	0	0	1	4	10
11/24/2022	14:45	0	0	1	2	0	1	5
11/24/2022	15:00	0	0	1	0	0	2	2
11/24/2022	15:15	0	0	0	0	1	1	5
11/24/2022	15:30	0	0	0	0	2	1	8
11/24/2022	15:45	0	0	0	0	1	2	4
11/24/2022	16:00	0	0	0	0	0	4	9
11/24/2022	16:15	0	0	0	1	1	4	7
11/24/2022	16:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
11/24/2022	16:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

11/24/2022	17:00	0	0	0	1	0	0	10
11/24/2022	17:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/24/2022	17:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	17:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/24/2022	18:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	18:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/24/2022	18:30	0	0	0	1	1	2	7
11/24/2022	18:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	19:00	0	0	0	0	1	2	3
11/24/2022	19:15	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
11/24/2022	19:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	19:45	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
11/24/2022	20:00	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11/24/2022	20:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
11/24/2022	20:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/24/2022	20:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	21:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	21:15	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
11/24/2022	21:30	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11/24/2022	21:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	22:00	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
11/24/2022	22:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	22:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	22:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	23:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	23:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	23:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	23:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24 Hr Summary		1	2	3	9	15	58	180

45 to <50	50 to <55	55 to <60	60 to <65	65 to <70	70 to <75	75 to <80	80 to <85	85 to <90
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2	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
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0	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
0	11	4	1	0	1	0	0	0
2	5	6	0	1	0	0	0	0
5	14	8	3	1	0	0	0	0
3	13	14	7	2	1	0	0	0
9	21	27	7	2	0	0	0	0
5	27	20	9	1	1	0	0	0
4	13	15	4	0	0	0	0	0
8	18	27	4	1	1	0	0	0
10	34	29	8	3	1	0	0	0
11	34	31	4	0	0	1	0	0
11	32	23	11	0	1	0	0	0
24	32	29	7	1	0	0	0	0
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7	40	17	10	2	0	0	0	0
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6	22	28	12	1	0	0	0	0
11	15	21	4	1	0	0	0	0
12	19	22	9	4	1	0	0	0
7	29	26	8	6	0	0	0	0
16	26	24	10	1	0	0	0	0
15	34	21	5	3	1	0	0	0
17	35	17	9	0	0	0	0	0
11	35	20	8	3	0	0	0	0
15	28	31	7	3	0	0	0	0
13	42	30	13	1	0	0	0	0
7	37	41	7	2	0	0	0	0
23	37	45	13	3	0	0	0	0
14	34	37	10	1	0	0	0	0

12	37	17	14	1	0	0	0	0
12	31	41	17	1	0	0	0	0
12	52	33	13	5	0	0	0	0
20	42	29	11	1	1	0	0	0
13	51	27	11	2	0	0	0	0
15	43	27	12	2	0	0	0	0
11	37	29	5	3	0	0	0	0
23	48	29	9	2	0	0	0	0
17	56	42	8	1	0	0	0	0
23	50	27	12	2	0	0	1	0
19	54	46	12	1	0	0	0	0
22	60	26	10	5	0	0	0	0
11	53	40	3	1	0	0	0	0
25	48	35	12	2	0	0	0	0
13	62	31	15	3	2	0	0	0
27	39	26	8	3	1	0	0	0
29	50	29	11	2	0	0	0	0
27	55	28	8	2	2	0	0	0
23	48	37	6	3	2	0	0	0
34	54	29	7	2	1	0	0	0
19	38	24	5	1	2	0	0	0
18	45	22	10	1	0	0	0	0
25	31	14	10	1	0	0	0	0
19	27	14	10	0	0	0	0	0
20	23	20	3	1	1	0	0	0
16	18	15	2	2	2	0	0	0
12	23	10	4	3	0	0	0	0
11	28	9	3	1	0	0	0	0
2	19	20	5	0	0	0	0	0
10	26	18	4	0	0	0	0	0
10	14	13	3	1	0	0	0	0
11	20	10	5	0	0	0	0	0
11	24	8	5	1	0	0	0	0
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5	18	11	3	0	0	0	0	0
5	14	4	2	0	0	1	0	0
2	9	6	3	0	0	1	0	0
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3	12	10	1	1	0	0	0	0
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45 to <50	50 to <55	55 to <60	60 to <65	65 to <70	70 to <75	75 to <80	80 to <85	85 to <90
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1	5	0	1	0	0	0	0	0

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2	7	2	1	0	0	0	0	0
7	12	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	19	9	2	0	1	0	0	0
17	19	13	7	1	0	0	0	0
11	31	13	3	1	0	0	0	0
7	21	7	6	3	0	0	0	0
9	27	14	2	0	1	0	0	0
19	27	23	8	0	0	0	0	0
14	52	10	5	7	1	0	0	0
16	31	21	6	0	0	0	0	0
15	25	25	13	3	0	0	0	0
11	27	25	7	2	1	0	1	0
10	34	20	17	1	0	0	0	0
7	22	38	4	5	0	0	0	0
4	20	19	9	2	0	0	0	0
12	25	11	6	1	0	0	0	0
6	29	31	10	2	0	0	0	0
10	32	26	4	4	0	0	0	0
3	32	15	9	1	0	0	0	0
12	27	25	13	0	0	0	0	0
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16	43	30	12	4	1	0	0	0
13	56	38	11	3	0	0	0	0
19	30	32	9	4	1	0	0	0
8	32	41	13	7	1	0	0	0
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11	44	26	14	1	1	0	0	0
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22	54	25	4	3	1	0	0	0
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24	42	26	3	5	1	0	0	0
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6	27	17	2	1	0	0	0	0
6	19	11	5	1	0	0	0	0
7	24	10	4	5	0	0	0	0
10	23	19	4	2	1	0	0	0
8	26	14	6	0	0	0	0	0
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6	28	11	3	1	1	0	0	0
5	17	12	1	1	0	0	0	0
4	11	7	0	2	0	0	0	0
8	9	10	1	1	0	0	0	0
6	9	8	0	1	0	0	0	0
3	15	11	2	0	0	0	0	0
1	8	10	1	2	0	0	0	0
3	14	4	0	1	0	0	0	0
2	4	4	0	1	0	0	0	0
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45 to <50	50 to <55	55 to <60	60 to <65	65 to <70	70 to <75	75 to <80	80 to <85	85 to <90
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2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
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0	1	2	1	0	0	1	0	0
0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
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0	1	3	1	1	0	0	0	0
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2	2	6	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	4	4	1	0	1	0	0	0
4	8	6	2	1	0	0	0	0
1	20	14	4	2	0	0	0	0
12	17	19	8	3	1	0	0	0
5	17	31	6	3	0	0	0	0
5	16	11	7	3	0	1	0	0
12	13	11	5	1	0	0	0	0
10	42	18	9	1	1	0	0	0
12	46	28	9	2	0	0	0	0
13	23	13	9	1	0	0	0	0
17	42	25	6	1	1	0	0	0
10	39	23	4	2	0	0	0	0
14	25	29	5	2	0	1	0	0
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12	16	12	4	1	0	0	0	0
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13	40	21	9	5	0	0	0	0
11	23	32	7	3	1	0	0	0
18	37	16	7	1	0	0	0	0
11	43	28	6	3	0	0	0	0
12	35	30	10	0	0	1	0	0
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12	40	30	9	2	0	0	0	0
20	41	33	10	1	0	0	0	0
11	43	35	14	4	0	0	0	0
19	48	37	7	1	0	0	0	0
18	35	35	12	4	2	0	0	0
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14	41	24	14	2	1	0	0	0
11	40	27	11	1	0	1	0	0
15	42	30	10	2	0	1	0	0
23	47	37	12	3	0	0	0	0
15	37	28	9	2	0	0	0	0
25	45	27	8	5	0	0	0	0
24	35	35	10	2	0	0	0	0
13	48	33	2	2	0	0	0	0
21	46	26	11	3	1	0	0	0
40	66	41	14	1	0	0	0	0
25	39	28	9	6	0	0	0	0

24	51	36	8	2	0	0	0	0
26	39	31	5	0	0	0	0	0
14	45	29	10	2	0	1	0	0
16	38	26	3	0	0	0	0	0
24	42	25	6	0	0	1	0	0
20	32	15	9	1	0	0	0	0
12	42	23	4	4	0	0	0	0
12	27	23	6	1	1	0	0	0
11	40	13	5	1	0	0	0	0
12	33	18	4	2	0	0	0	0
5	24	23	6	2	0	1	0	0
9	23	14	2	4	1	0	0	0
4	17	13	7	1	0	0	0	0
9	11	23	4	1	0	1	1	0
12	14	18	8	1	0	0	0	0
5	11	13	6	3	2	1	0	0
13	24	21	5	1	0	0	0	0
7	15	11	4	2	0	0	0	0
3	14	14	4	1	0	0	0	0
5	13	7	2	1	0	0	0	0
7	8	15	4	0	2	1	0	0
2	12	7	2	0	1	0	0	0
3	9	6	2	2	1	0	0	0
2	7	8	3	1	1	0	0	0
2	5	6	5	1	0	0	0	0
1	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
1	5	5	3	0	0	0	0	0
3	2	4	1	0	0	0	0	0
891	2228	1662	519	135	28	13	1	0

022-12-00-AM to Thu-Nov-24-2022-11-59-PM

90 to <95	95 to <100	100 to <105	105 to <110	110 to <115	115 to >120	Total Counts
0	0	0	0	0	0	10
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	8
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	6
0	0	0	0	0	0	6
0	0	0	0	0	0	17
0	0	0	0	0	0	14
0	0	0	0	0	0	31
0	0	0	0	0	0	41
0	0	0	0	0	0	68
0	0	0	0	0	0	66
0	0	0	0	0	0	38
0	0	0	0	0	0	61
0	0	0	0	0	0	90
0	0	0	0	0	0	84
0	0	0	0	0	0	80
0	0	0	0	0	0	97
0	0	0	0	0	0	62
0	0	0	0	0	0	79
0	0	0	0	0	0	60
0	0	0	0	0	0	69
0	0	0	0	0	0	54
0	0	0	0	0	0	69
0	0	0	0	0	0	78
0	0	0	0	0	0	77
0	0	0	0	0	0	81
0	0	0	0	0	0	81
0	0	0	0	0	0	79
0	0	0	0	0	0	90
0	0	0	0	0	0	101
0	0	0	0	0	0	96
0	0	0	0	0	0	135
0	0	0	0	0	0	102

0	0	0	0	0	0	87
0	0	0	0	0	0	107
0	0	0	0	0	0	117
0	0	0	0	0	0	105
0	0	0	0	0	0	107
0	0	0	0	0	0	103
0	0	0	0	0	0	94
0	0	0	0	0	0	119
0	0	0	0	0	0	129
0	0	0	0	0	0	120
0	0	0	0	0	0	134
0	0	0	0	0	0	127
0	0	0	0	0	0	118
0	0	0	0	0	0	128
0	0	0	0	0	0	133
0	0	0	0	0	0	113
0	0	0	0	0	0	135
0	0	0	0	0	0	126
0	0	0	0	0	0	130
0	0	0	0	0	0	137
0	0	0	0	0	0	96
0	0	0	0	0	0	98
0	0	0	0	0	0	86
0	0	0	0	0	0	73
0	0	0	0	0	0	78
0	0	0	0	0	0	62
0	0	0	0	0	0	53
0	0	0	0	0	0	59
0	0	0	0	0	0	52
0	0	0	0	0	0	62
0	0	0	0	0	0	46
0	0	0	0	0	0	52
0	0	0	0	0	0	53
0	0	0	0	0	0	44
0	0	0	0	0	0	49
0	0	0	0	0	0	38
0	0	0	0	0	0	26
0	0	0	0	0	0	23
0	0	0	0	0	0	25
0	0	0	0	0	0	27
0	0	0	0	0	0	22
0	0	0	0	0	0	24
0	0	0	0	0	0	19
0	0	0	0	0	0	15
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	13
0	0	0	0	0	0	5659

90 to <95	95 to <100	100 to <105	105 to <110	110 to <115	115 to >120	Total Counts
1	0	0	0	0	0	14
0	0	0	0	0	0	13
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	8

0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	8
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	18
0	0	0	0	0	0	13
0	0	0	0	0	0	24
0	0	0	0	0	0	36
0	0	0	0	0	0	60
0	0	0	0	0	0	61
0	0	0	0	0	0	45
0	0	0	0	0	0	55
0	0	0	0	0	0	82
0	0	0	0	0	0	98
0	0	0	0	0	0	78
0	0	0	0	0	0	90
0	0	0	0	0	0	75
0	0	0	0	0	0	84
0	0	0	0	0	0	77
0	0	0	0	0	0	54
0	0	0	0	0	0	59
0	0	0	0	0	0	82
0	0	0	0	0	0	80
0	0	0	0	0	0	64
0	0	0	0	0	0	79
0	0	0	0	0	0	99
0	0	0	0	0	0	92
0	0	0	0	0	0	87
0	0	0	0	0	0	125
0	0	0	0	0	0	109
0	0	0	0	0	0	126
0	0	0	0	0	0	98
0	0	0	0	0	0	107
0	0	0	0	0	0	103
0	0	0	0	0	0	96
0	0	0	0	0	0	102
0	0	0	0	0	0	116
0	0	0	0	0	0	113
0	0	0	0	0	0	100
0	0	0	0	0	0	113
0	0	0	0	0	0	111

0	0	0	0	0	0	130
0	0	0	0	0	0	91
0	0	0	0	0	0	123
0	0	0	0	0	0	108
0	0	0	0	0	0	115
0	0	0	0	0	0	125
0	0	0	0	0	0	104
0	0	0	0	0	0	151
0	0	0	0	0	0	112
0	0	0	0	0	0	122
0	0	0	0	0	0	106
0	0	0	0	0	0	106
0	0	0	0	0	0	78
0	0	0	0	0	0	77
0	0	0	0	0	0	77
0	0	0	0	0	0	68
0	0	0	0	0	0	60
0	0	0	0	0	0	71
0	0	0	0	0	0	57
0	0	0	0	0	0	54
0	0	0	0	0	0	48
0	0	0	0	0	0	54
0	0	0	0	0	0	61
0	0	0	0	0	0	56
0	0	0	0	0	0	44
0	0	0	0	0	0	42
0	0	0	0	0	0	50
0	0	0	0	0	0	39
0	0	0	0	0	0	28
0	0	0	0	0	0	29
0	0	0	0	0	0	27
0	0	0	0	0	0	31
0	0	0	0	0	0	22
0	0	0	0	0	0	22
0	0	0	0	0	0	12
0	0	0	0	0	0	9
0	0	0	0	0	0	9
1	0	0	0	0	0	5619

90 to <95	95 to <100	100 to <105	105 to <110	110 to <115	115 to >120	Total Counts
0	0	0	0	0	0	8
0	0	0	0	0	0	9
0	0	0	0	0	0	10
0	0	0	0	0	0	10
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	6
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	1

0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	6
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	14
0	0	0	0	0	0	9
0	0	0	0	0	0	11
0	0	0	0	0	0	13
0	0	0	0	0	0	22
0	0	0	0	0	0	41
0	0	0	0	0	0	64
0	0	0	0	0	0	62
0	0	0	0	0	0	43
0	0	0	0	0	0	45
0	0	0	0	0	0	85
0	0	0	0	0	0	100
0	0	0	0	0	0	60
0	0	0	0	0	0	99
0	0	0	0	0	0	80
0	0	0	0	0	0	79
0	0	0	0	0	0	69
0	0	0	0	0	0	45
0	0	0	0	0	0	72
0	0	0	0	0	0	84
0	0	0	0	0	0	79
0	0	0	0	0	0	92
0	0	0	0	0	0	79
0	0	0	0	0	0	82
0	0	0	0	0	0	95
0	0	0	0	0	0	90
0	0	0	0	0	0	114
0	0	0	0	0	0	123
0	0	0	0	0	0	101
0	0	0	0	0	0	97
0	0	0	0	0	0	107
0	0	0	0	0	0	109
0	0	0	0	0	0	115
0	0	0	0	0	0	108
0	0	0	0	0	0	103
0	0	0	0	0	0	95
0	0	0	0	0	0	86
0	0	0	0	0	0	105
0	0	0	0	0	0	106
0	0	0	0	0	0	109
0	0	0	0	0	0	127
0	0	0	0	0	0	98
0	0	0	0	0	0	121
0	0	0	0	0	0	113
0	0	0	0	0	0	111
0	0	0	0	0	0	121
0	0	0	0	0	0	171
0	0	0	0	0	0	108

0	0	0	0	0	0	132
0	0	0	0	0	0	107
0	0	0	0	0	0	103
0	0	0	0	0	0	87
0	0	0	0	0	0	100
0	0	0	0	0	0	81
0	0	0	0	0	0	96
0	0	0	0	0	0	73
0	0	0	0	0	0	76
0	0	0	0	0	0	71
0	0	0	0	0	0	62
0	0	0	0	0	0	55
0	0	0	0	0	0	44
0	0	0	0	0	0	58
0	0	0	0	0	0	54
0	0	0	0	0	0	42
0	0	0	0	0	0	65
0	0	0	0	0	0	40
0	0	0	0	0	0	38
0	0	0	0	0	0	29
0	0	0	0	0	0	39
0	0	0	0	0	0	25
0	0	0	0	0	0	24
0	0	0	0	0	0	22
0	0	0	0	0	0	20
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	14
0	0	0	0	0	0	10
0	0	0	0	0	0	5745

Avg Speed (km/h)	85pct Speed	10km/h Pace	% in pace	# of Speeders	% Speeders	VEH_SM
-1	60	50 to 60	70.0	8	80.0	0
-1	59	49 to 59	80.0	5	100.0	0
-1	75	65 to 75	66.7	3	100.0	0
56.9	56	46 to 56	85.7	5	71.4	0
-1	58	49 to 59	75.0	3	75.0	0
-1	54	45 to 55	75.0	2	50.0	0
-1	52	42 to 52	100.0	1	100.0	0
52.3	56	46 to 56	100.0	3	100.0	0
-1	55	45 to 55	100.0	1	100.0	0
-1	58	48 to 58	87.5	7	87.5	0
-1	60	50 to 60	100.0	3	100.0	0
56	61	51 to 61	100.0	2	100.0	0
-1	55	53 to 63	75.0	3	75.0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-1	55	46 to 56	80.0	3	60.0	0
51.5	49	39 to 49	100.0	0	0	0
-1	59	49 to 59	80.0	5	100.0	0
-1	49	39 to 49	100.0	0	0	0
-1	53	43 to 53	80.0	2	40.0	0
55	55	48 to 58	100.0	5	100.0	0
-1	55	47 to 57	100.0	6	100.0	0
-1	59.5	42 to 52	66.7	4	66.7	0
-1	57	48 to 58	88.2	16	94.1	0
54.3	57	47 to 57	85.7	11	78.6	0
-1	58	47 to 57	80.6	24	77.4	0
-1	60	52 to 62	80.5	36	87.8	0
-1	58	50 to 60	75.0	53	77.9	0
54.5	59.3	50 to 60	75.8	51	77.3	0
-1	58.3	49 to 59	76.3	31	81.6	0
-1	58.4	49 to 59	77.0	46	75.4	0
-1	58.7	49 to 59	75.6	70	77.8	0
53.9	57	48 to 58	85.7	64	76.2	0
-1	59	50 to 60	76.3	63	78.8	0
-1	57	47 to 57	78.4	67	69.1	0
-1	59.8	50 to 60	71.0	48	77.4	0
53.7	58	48 to 58	78.5	67	84.8	1
-1	58	48 to 58	80.0	46	76.7	0
-1	59.4	50 to 60	82.6	61	88.4	0
-1	58.2	47 to 57	75.9	36	66.7	0
54.3	60.5	47 to 57	68.1	53	76.8	0
-1	59.7	51 to 61	75.6	66	84.6	0
-1	58.7	47 to 57	75.3	59	76.6	0
-1	57.5	47 to 57	80.2	57	70.4	0
53.7	58	47 to 57	75.3	54	66.7	0
-1	58.9	49 to 59	75.9	58	73.4	0
-1	57.6	49 to 59	75.6	67	74.4	0
-1	58.8	48 to 58	75.2	79	78.2	0
54	58.2	50 to 60	85.4	82	85.4	0
-1	58.5	50 to 60	64.4	91	67.4	0
-1	58.5	49 to 59	76.5	79	77.5	0

-1	59.5	47 to 57	67.8	61	70.1	0
53.3	59.3	51 to 61	76.6	89	83.2	1
-1	59	48 to 58	77.8	98	83.8	0
-1	58	48 to 58	80.0	75	71.4	0
-1	58.4	48 to 58	78.5	84	78.5	0
53.8	58.7	48 to 58	76.7	74	71.8	0
-1	58	49 to 59	74.5	71	75.5	0
-1	56	46 to 56	74.8	83	69.7	0
-1	56.6	47 to 57	81.4	99	76.7	0
53	58.4	48 to 58	72.5	85	70.8	0
-1	57.9	49 to 59	80.6	103	76.9	0
-1	56.8	47 to 57	78.7	92	72.4	0
-1	56.9	49 to 59	83.1	91	77.1	0
53.1	57.8	47 to 57	75.0	85	66.4	0
-1	59	49 to 59	73.7	105	78.9	0
-1	57.7	46 to 56	69.0	72	63.7	1
-1	57.2	48 to 58	68.1	81	60.0	0
52.5	55.9	46 to 56	78.6	82	65.1	0
-1	57	47 to 57	72.3	83	63.8	0
-1	56.7	48 to 58	75.9	79	57.7	0
-1	56.7	47 to 57	79.2	59	61.5	0
52.4	56.6	47 to 57	83.7	68	69.4	0
-1	58	45 to 55	70.9	48	55.8	0
-1	58.7	46 to 56	74.0	46	63.0	0
-1	56.7	46 to 56	66.7	45	57.7	0
51.9	58.2	46 to 56	61.3	36	58.1	0
-1	57.7	45 to 55	77.4	38	71.7	0
-1	55.5	47 to 57	76.3	38	64.4	0
-1	57.5	50 to 60	76.9	42	80.8	0
52.5	57	47 to 57	74.2	45	72.6	0
-1	57	48 to 58	71.7	30	65.2	0
-1	55.7	47 to 57	75.0	30	57.7	0
-1	57	47 to 57	71.7	33	62.3	0
52.2	58	48 to 58	75.0	31	70.5	0
-1	57.3	48 to 58	81.6	35	71.4	0
-1	56.5	47 to 57	78.9	27	71.1	0
-1	56	49 to 59	84.6	20	76.9	0
53.4	60	50 to 60	69.6	17	73.9	0
-1	55.5	46 to 56	76.0	15	60.0	0
-1	57.5	48 to 58	88.9	22	81.5	0
-1	62	50 to 60	72.7	19	86.4	0
54.5	64	48 to 58	70.8	20	83.3	0
-1	60	47 to 57	68.4	14	73.7	0
-1	58	48 to 58	86.7	10	66.7	0
-1	51	41 to 51	80.0	3	60.0	0
53.8	55	45 to 55	76.9	6	46.2	0
12.6	59	48 to 58	72.6	4095	72.4	3

Avg Speed (km/h)	85pct Speed	10km/h Pace	% in pace	# of Speeders	% Speeders	VEH_SM
-1	57	47 to 57	78.6	11	78.6	0
-1	60	47 to 57	69.2	10	76.9	0
-1	61	55 to 65	100.0	4	100.0	0
55.7	42	32 to 42	100.0	0	0	0
-1	53	43 to 53	75.0	6	75.0	0

-1	58	48 to 58	100.0	1	100.0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
54.2	62	52 to 62	100.0	3	100.0	0
-1	63	53 to 63	100.0	1	100.0	0
-1	58	24 to 34	50.0	1	50.0	0
-1	77	49 to 59	66.7	3	100.0	0
56.6	57	50 to 60	100.0	4	100.0	0
-1	68	58 to 68	100.0	1	100.0	0
-1	63	53 to 63	100.0	1	100.0	0
-1	67	57 to 67	100.0	1	100.0	0
59.5	54	44 to 54	100.0	3	100.0	0
-1	58	48 to 58	75.0	3	75.0	0
-1	64	54 to 64	100.0	2	100.0	0
-1	58	39 to 49	50.0	2	50.0	0
54.8	54	45 to 55	100.0	3	60.0	0
-1	57	47 to 57	87.5	5	62.5	0
-1	51	41 to 51	85.7	3	42.9	0
-1	55	47 to 57	88.9	14	77.8	0
52.5	57	44 to 54	69.2	10	76.9	0
-1	53.5	44 to 54	83.3	12	50.0	0
-1	58	50 to 60	83.3	25	69.4	0
-1	58	46 to 56	75.0	38	63.3	0
52.4	56.8	48 to 58	83.6	44	72.1	0
-1	61	47 to 57	71.1	36	80.0	0
-1	56.8	47 to 57	81.8	36	65.5	0
-1	56.6	47 to 57	75.6	51	62.2	0
52.6	57	45 to 55	71.4	66	67.3	0
-1	56.4	47 to 57	78.2	56	71.8	0
-1	59.4	50 to 60	61.1	63	70.0	0
-1	59	48 to 58	76.0	58	77.3	0
53.6	60	49 to 59	71.4	66	78.6	0
-1	58.6	49 to 59	83.1	66	85.7	0
-1	60.3	49 to 59	75.9	46	85.2	0
-1	57	47 to 57	76.3	37	62.7	1
54.3	59	49 to 59	76.8	69	84.1	0
-1	57.8	48 to 58	76.3	64	80.0	0
-1	59	50 to 60	81.3	51	79.7	0
-1	59.5	49 to 59	74.7	63	79.7	0
54.1	59	49 to 59	74.7	82	82.8	1
-1	58.3	47 to 57	72.8	65	70.7	0
-1	60.2	51 to 61	67.8	68	78.2	0
-1	59.2	47 to 57	74.4	103	82.4	0
54.1	60	48 to 58	74.3	83	76.1	0
-1	58	49 to 59	77.8	91	72.2	0
-1	58.8	50 to 60	69.4	71	72.4	0
-1	60.4	51 to 61	73.8	91	85.0	0
53.8	59	47 to 57	66.0	72	69.9	1
-1	57.3	49 to 59	84.4	78	81.3	0
-1	59.3	51 to 61	72.5	82	80.4	1
-1	59.9	48 to 58	71.6	91	78.4	0
53.9	57.2	48 to 58	82.3	88	77.9	1
-1	58	48 to 58	73.0	69	69.0	0
-1	60.3	48 to 58	66.4	85	75.2	0
-1	57.7	48 to 58	73.0	87	78.4	0

53.9	58	51 to 61	77.7	107	82.3	0
-1	58.3	51 to 61	73.6	76	83.5	0
-1	58.4	49 to 59	74.0	92	74.8	0
-1	57	47 to 57	73.1	72	66.7	0
52.9	56.2	47 to 57	80.9	71	61.7	0
-1	57.6	48 to 58	84.0	97	77.6	0
-1	56.8	47 to 57	69.2	60	57.7	0
-1	55.7	46 to 56	71.5	82	54.3	0
51.9	56.9	47 to 57	68.8	71	63.4	0
-1	56.2	47 to 57	74.6	79	64.8	0
-1	59	47 to 57	72.6	78	73.6	0
-1	56.5	46 to 56	75.5	71	67.0	0
52.6	58	48 to 58	69.2	53	67.9	1
-1	56.6	47 to 57	79.2	57	74.0	0
-1	57.7	47 to 57	72.7	52	67.5	0
-1	56.8	48 to 58	83.8	53	77.9	0
52.7	57.5	48 to 58	76.7	39	65.0	0
-1	55.7	46 to 56	77.5	42	59.2	0
-1	55.8	46 to 56	78.9	31	54.4	0
-1	57.2	49 to 59	87.0	45	83.3	0
52.5	57.5	48 to 58	72.9	32	66.7	0
-1	60	48 to 58	68.5	39	72.2	0
-1	57.5	48 to 58	75.4	43	70.5	0
-1	56.8	48 to 58	78.6	41	73.2	0
53	56	47 to 57	81.8	29	65.9	0
-1	59	48 to 58	73.8	32	76.2	0
-1	57	48 to 58	86.0	41	82.0	0
-1	56.7	47 to 57	79.5	28	71.8	0
53.2	55.5	47 to 57	78.6	19	67.9	0
-1	57	46 to 56	82.8	17	58.6	0
-1	56.3	47 to 57	81.5	17	63.0	0
-1	56	49 to 59	87.1	25	80.6	0
53.5	59	49 to 59	81.8	19	86.4	0
-1	58.3	49 to 59	86.4	15	68.2	0
-1	58	48 to 58	75.0	8	66.7	0
-1	61	51 to 61	88.9	9	100.0	0
54.4	56	46 to 56	77.8	8	88.9	0
12.8	58	48 to 58	72.9	4095	72.9	6

Avg Speed (km/h)	85pct Speed	10km/h Pace	% in pace	# of Speeders	% Speeders	VEH_SM
-1	62	48 to 58	62.5	6	75.0	0
-1	62	49 to 59	66.7	7	77.8	0
-1	57	47 to 57	60.0	7	70.0	0
55.7	63	44 to 54	60.0	9	90.0	0
-1	51	48 to 58	100.0	2	40.0	0
-1	56	46 to 56	80.0	5	100.0	0
-1	53	43 to 53	75.0	2	50.0	0
55.1	61	51 to 61	75.0	4	100.0	0
-1	59	52 to 62	85.7	6	85.7	0
-1	61	51 to 61	71.4	6	85.7	0
-1	70	44 to 54	66.7	2	66.7	0
57.6	64	47 to 57	50.0	5	83.3	0
-1	61	51 to 61	100.0	1	100.0	0
-1	53	43 to 53	100.0	1	100.0	0

-1	64	44 to 54	66.7	3	100.0	0
54.8	58	48 to 58	85.7	5	71.4	0
-1	62	52 to 62	83.3	6	100.0	0
-1	54	37 to 47	66.7	1	33.3	0
-1	54	44 to 54	80.0	3	60.0	0
53.3	55	49 to 59	80.0	4	80.0	0
-1	55	47 to 57	92.9	9	64.3	0
-1	60	50 to 60	88.9	7	77.8	0
-1	56.5	47 to 57	90.9	8	72.7	0
53.4	58	47 to 57	69.2	9	69.2	0
-1	59	48 to 58	72.7	16	72.7	0
-1	59	49 to 59	85.4	37	90.2	0
-1	59.7	47 to 57	68.8	47	73.4	0
54.9	59	49 to 59	82.3	55	88.7	0
-1	61	49 to 59	69.8	34	79.1	0
-1	58.5	45 to 55	64.4	29	64.4	0
-1	58.3	47 to 57	75.3	60	70.6	0
53.7	58.3	49 to 59	78.0	79	79.0	0
-1	59.2	47 to 57	70.0	42	70.0	0
-1	56.9	48 to 58	74.7	73	73.7	0
-1	56.7	48 to 58	83.8	58	72.5	0
53.2	58.4	49 to 59	74.7	59	74.7	0
-1	57	48 to 58	82.6	55	79.7	0
-1	58	47 to 57	82.2	31	68.9	0
-1	60.5	49 to 59	76.4	59	81.9	0
54.1	56.8	49 to 59	84.5	71	84.5	0
-1	58	49 to 59	78.5	58	73.4	0
-1	59	48 to 58	73.9	67	72.8	0
-1	58.7	48 to 58	74.7	64	81.0	0
53.5	56.3	47 to 57	80.5	53	64.6	0
-1	58.2	49 to 59	80.0	73	76.8	0
-1	58	48 to 58	77.8	70	77.8	0
-1	59.5	47 to 57	71.1	83	72.8	0
53.8	58.4	49 to 59	74.0	100	81.3	0
-1	57.4	48 to 58	80.2	77	76.2	0
-1	58.3	49 to 59	76.3	77	79.4	0
-1	57.6	48 to 58	76.6	78	72.9	0
53.7	59.5	49 to 59	77.1	87	79.8	1
-1	56.5	47 to 57	84.3	89	77.4	0
-1	59.7	47 to 57	74.1	83	76.9	0
-1	59.4	51 to 61	80.6	89	86.4	0
53.9	58.2	49 to 59	73.7	67	70.5	0
-1	58	50 to 60	88.4	78	90.7	0
-1	59.1	47 to 57	69.5	73	69.5	0
-1	57.7	49 to 59	66.0	74	69.8	0
53.1	58.6	50 to 60	70.6	81	74.3	0
-1	57.5	47 to 57	77.2	93	73.2	0
-1	58	50 to 60	71.4	68	69.4	0
-1	57.2	46 to 56	71.9	80	66.1	0
52.7	57.8	48 to 58	73.5	75	66.4	0
-1	55.7	48 to 58	79.3	79	71.2	0
-1	58	47 to 57	65.3	76	62.8	1
-1	57.5	46 to 56	73.7	111	64.9	0
52.5	58.8	46 to 56	74.1	75	69.4	0

-1	57	49 to 59	71.2	89	67.4	0
-1	56.6	46 to 56	76.6	72	67.3	0
-1	58.7	47 to 57	74.8	83	80.6	0
52.8	55.6	47 to 57	83.9	63	72.4	0
-1	57.2	49 to 59	80.0	63	63.0	0
-1	58	46 to 56	74.1	52	64.2	0
-1	56	46 to 56	72.9	63	65.6	0
52.6	58.2	49 to 59	71.2	55	75.3	0
-1	57	49 to 59	78.9	52	68.4	0
-1	57.2	48 to 58	78.9	52	73.2	0
-1	59	49 to 59	77.4	52	83.9	0
53.4	58.5	46 to 56	74.5	42	76.4	1
-1	59.3	50 to 60	75.0	38	86.4	0
-1	57.6	48 to 58	69.0	41	70.7	0
-1	59.3	48 to 58	74.1	41	75.9	0
54.5	63	48 to 58	66.7	35	83.3	0
-1	56.3	47 to 57	80.0	46	70.8	0
-1	59	48 to 58	67.5	29	72.5	0
-1	58.8	49 to 59	78.9	33	86.8	0
53.6	58	45 to 55	72.4	20	69.0	0
-1	59.3	51 to 61	69.2	30	76.9	0
-1	57	48 to 58	84.0	20	80.0	0
-1	60	48 to 58	70.8	19	79.2	0
55	61	51 to 61	72.7	19	86.4	0
-1	61.5	52 to 62	70.0	17	85.0	0
-1	60	45 to 55	71.4	5	71.4	0
-1	60	51 to 61	85.7	12	85.7	0
55.4	57.5	48 to 58	90.0	7	70.0	0
12.5	59	48 to 58	73.1	4251	74.0	3

VEH_MED	VEH_LG
10	0
5	0
3	0
5	2
4	0
4	0
1	0
3	0
1	0
8	0
3	0
2	0
4	0
0	0
2	3
1	0
5	0
2	0
5	0
5	0
6	0
6	0
16	1
14	0
31	0
41	0
68	0
65	1
37	1
58	3
85	5
79	5
76	4
94	3
60	2
77	1
59	1
66	3
52	2
69	0
74	4
73	4
77	4
79	2
76	3
87	3
99	2
95	1
133	2
100	2

86	1
103	3
114	3
99	6
106	1
102	1
91	3
117	2
127	2
119	1
133	1
122	4
118	1
127	1
131	2
111	1
133	2
126	0
128	2
136	1
95	1
96	2
86	0
72	1
78	0
61	1
51	2
57	2
52	0
61	1
46	0
51	1
53	0
43	1
45	4
36	2
26	0
23	0
22	3
27	0
22	0
24	0
19	0
15	0
4	1
13	0
5532	124

Page 1

VEH_MED	VEH_LG
13	1
13	0
4	0
1	0
7	1

1	0
0	0
3	0
1	0
2	0
2	1
4	0
1	0
1	0
1	0
2	1
3	1
2	0
4	0
5	0
7	1
7	0
18	0
12	1
23	1
35	1
57	3
60	1
41	4
54	1
81	1
96	2
76	2
84	6
74	1
80	4
75	2
50	3
58	1
79	2
79	2
62	2
76	3
98	0
89	3
85	1
123	3
108	1
123	3
94	4
105	2
100	2
95	1
98	3
112	4
108	4
99	1
109	4
109	2

126	4
89	2
121	2
103	5
112	3
122	3
102	2
150	1
112	0
119	1
107	1
105	1
77	0
76	1
75	1
69	0
58	2
71	0
56	1
54	0
48	0
54	0
60	1
56	0
44	0
40	1
51	0
39	0
27	1
29	0
25	1
30	2
22	0
22	0
12	0
9	0
8	1
5489	124

Page 2

VEH_MED	VEH_LG
8	0
9	0
10	0
9	1
5	0
5	0
4	0
4	0
7	0
7	0
3	0
6	0
1	0
1	0

3	0
7	0
6	0
3	0
5	0
5	0
13	1
9	0
11	0
12	1
21	1
41	0
64	0
60	2
41	2
44	1
85	0
98	2
55	5
96	3
78	2
75	4
68	1
43	2
70	2
83	1
78	1
89	3
76	3
81	1
93	2
88	2
112	2
122	1
99	2
94	3
102	5
105	3
112	3
107	1
103	0
94	1
85	1
103	2
106	0
106	3
127	0
97	1
116	5
110	3
110	1
119	1
166	5
108	0

132	0
106	1
102	1
86	1
98	2
79	1
97	0
72	1
76	0
69	2
62	0
54	0
44	0
57	1
53	1
42	0
64	1
40	0
37	1
25	4
38	1
25	0
24	0
22	0
20	0
7	0
14	0
10	0
5638	104

Incoming-Daily Volume for Daily Vehicle Counts

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB
Daily Volumes

Vehicles

7,000

6,000

5,000

4,000

3,000

2,000

1,000

0

Monday

Tuesday

Wednesday

Thursday

Day						
Friday						
Saturday						
Sunday						

Zoom
help

Average Vehicle Speed (km/h) vs. Time [13 Street S

23
20
PM
3:00 PM
4:00 PM
5:00 PM
6:00 PM
7:00 PM
8:00 PM
9:00 PM
10:00 PM
11:00 PM
Thursday 24
1:00 AM
2:00 AM
3:00 AM
4:00 AM
5:00 AM
6:00 AM
7:00 AM
8:00 AM
9:00 AM
10:00 AM
11:00 AM
12:00 PM
1:00 PM
2:00 PM
3:00 PM
4:00 PM
5:00 PM
6:00 PM
7:00 PM
8:00 PM
9:00 PM
10:00 PM
11:00 PM
Friday 25
Thursday 24

Zoom
help

17,023 Counts

120
Percentile Counts Vs. Speed for [13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB: Incoming]

85th Pct Speed=59.0 km/h
Vehicle in data=17023
11/22/2022 12:00:00 AM to 11/24/2022 11:59:59 PM

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - SB

Wc And Ambient Temperature

Date&Time	Speed	Class	Direction
11/22/2022 12:01:17 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:02:24 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:02:26 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:02:51 AM	45.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:07:32 AM	68.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:10:43 AM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:12:14 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:12:25 AM	64.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:13:32 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:14:17 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:19:23 AM	66.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:21:59 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:22:13 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:28:58 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:29:27 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:33:37 AM	75.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:34:01 AM	67.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:36:55 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:46:28 AM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:46:35 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:48:07 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:51:14 AM	49.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:52:11 AM	65.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:57:10 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:59:08 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:01:07 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:10:14 AM	41.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:10:49 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:13:24 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:22:29 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:22:47 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:26:34 AM	37.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:28:06 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:33:53 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:45:02 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:47:55 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:52:51 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:08:49 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:16:34 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:16:58 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:18:39 AM	48.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:19:46 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:21:14 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:27:29 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:27:43 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:28:09 AM	66.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:36:45 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:38:35 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:44:21 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:46:01 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:54:38 AM	61.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:02:09 AM	63.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:03:41 AM	38.0	Medium	Incoming

11/22/2022 3:04:28 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:08:21 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:31:34 AM	56.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:32:52 AM	43.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:35:06 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:36:43 AM	49.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:36:44 AM	52.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:57:17 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:02:39 AM	66.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:05:51 AM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:06:46 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:08:14 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:08:29 AM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:16:49 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:25:44 AM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:30:39 AM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:31:05 AM	46.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:35:43 AM	76.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:43:04 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:44:25 AM	46.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:48:05 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:48:20 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:50:11 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:54:03 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:57:17 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:01:16 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:03:23 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:06:17 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:08:49 AM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:08:52 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:13:24 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:22:47 AM	42.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:23:13 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:24:46 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:25:27 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:26:00 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:26:05 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:30:46 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:30:53 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:32:49 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:35:20 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:35:22 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:35:31 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:37:45 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:38:04 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:38:54 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:39:02 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:39:14 AM	57.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:40:30 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:41:10 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:41:37 AM	64.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:43:04 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:43:47 AM	74.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:43:54 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming

11/22/2022 5:46:50 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:48:02 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:49:04 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:49:27 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:51:39 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:51:49 AM	65.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:52:22 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:53:07 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/23/2022 10:00:37 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/23/2022 10:08:53 AM	48.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/23/2022 10:23:23 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/23/2022 10:42:50 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/23/2022 10:42:52 AM	53.0	Large	Incoming
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11/23/2022 10:58:36 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/23/2022 11:02:27 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/23/2022 11:02:31 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
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